

**THE ROLE OF CHRISTIAN RELIGIOUS STUDIES IN
CURBING MORAL DECADENCE AMONG SECONDARY
STUDENTS IN ODEDA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA,
OGUN STATE**

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Abstract

Moral decadence among secondary school students in Nigeria is a growing concern, with rising cases of indiscipline, corruption, examination malpractice, and drug abuse. The erosion of ethical values poses a threat to societal stability and national development. This study examines the role of Christian Religious Studies (CRS) in addressing moral decline among students in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. Using a survey research design, data were collected through structured questionnaires to assess students' perceptions of CRS in promoting moral values. Findings reveal that CRS helps shape students' ethical consciousness, instill discipline, and discourage delinquent behavior. However, challenges such as inadequate instructional materials, limited teacher training, and declining student interest hinder its effectiveness. The study recommends integrating moral education into the school curriculum, strengthening CRS programs, and fostering collaboration among schools, religious institutions, and parents to reinforce ethical teachings. Strengthening CRS will help develop a morally upright generation and ensure societal transformation.

Keywords: Christian Religious Studies, Moral Decay, Secondary Education, Ethical Values, Societal Transformation, Ogun State.

Introduction

Moral decadence among youths has been a growing concern in Nigeria. The increasing involvement of secondary school students in various forms of immorality, such as sexual misconduct, cybercrime, cultism, and drug abuse, calls for urgent attention. Moral values are essential for regulating behavior and maintaining social order within societies (Yudkin *et al.*, 2021). However, globalization and technological advancements have significantly contributed to the decline in moral standards, influencing young individuals through social media, peer pressure, and exposure to diverse cultural ideologies that may contradict traditional moral values (McKenzie 2024).

Education has long been recognized as a fundamental tool for shaping the character and ethical perspectives of students. Christian Religious Studies (CRS) aims to provide moral guidance, drawing from biblical teachings to promote good behavior and discourage deviant acts (Ogbodo and Shanpepe, 2025). In particular, it serves as a moral compass by instilling virtues such as honesty, integrity, and responsibility in students. Given the rise in youth delinquency and moral laxity in Nigeria, examining the role of CRS in curbing moral decadence becomes imperative. This study seeks to explore the effectiveness of CRS in fostering ethical behavior and discouraging social vices among secondary school students in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Statement of the Problem

Moral decline among secondary school students in Nigeria, especially in the Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, has become a serious concern. Issues like drug abuse, cultism, cheating in exams, disrespect for authority, and cybercrime indicate a troubling decline in ethical values. Although Christian Religious Studies (CRS) has been included in the school curriculum to promote moral values, its success in addressing these societal problems seems limited. Factors such as peer pressure, lack of parental involvement, negative media influences, and poor enforcement of religious education contribute to this situation. It is crucial to assess the effectiveness of CRS in shaping students' moral awareness and to find ways to enhance its influence in the face of increasing moral challenges.

Research Questions

1. How does Christian Religious Studies (CRS) shape students' understanding and application of moral values in secondary schools within the Odeda Local Government Area?
2. What specific signs of moral decline are common among secondary school students in Odeda LGA, and how well does CRS address these issues?

3. What challenges hinder the effectiveness of CRS in combating moral decline, and what strategies can be put in place to enhance its impact?

Significance of the Study

The findings and recommendations from this study will be valuable to the following stakeholders in these ways:

Ministry of Education:

1. Inform policy changes to integrate strong moral education through CRS.
2. Guide curriculum updates to focus on character development.

Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC):

1. Assist in creating relevant CRS content that tackles current moral issues.
2. Provide data to support curriculum evaluations and the development of instructional materials.

Secondary Schools:

1. Strengthen efforts to promote discipline and moral responsibility.
2. Supply data for implementing effective moral education programs.

School Administration:

1. Aid in developing school-based strategies and policies to address moral decline.
2. Encourage partnerships with religious organizations for student character development.

Teachers of CRS:

1. Provide insights for improving teaching methods and classroom practices for moral education.
2. Promote the application of biblical principles in real-life situations.

Teachers in Charge of Discipline:

1. Equip them with knowledge on how CRS can enhance disciplinary approaches.
2. Help identify the underlying moral issues contributing to indiscipline for targeted solutions.

Teachers in Charge of Guidance and Counselling:

1. Offer resources for incorporating moral and spiritual guidance into counselling sessions.

2. Support early detection and intervention for behavioral problems.
Students:
 1. Promote ethical decision-making, personal responsibility, and a sense of community.
 2. Help reduce susceptibility to peer pressure, cults, substance abuse, and other negative influences.Parents:
 1. Actively support their children's moral and spiritual growth.
 2. Recognize their vital role in reinforcing the values taught in schools.The Church:
 1. Enhance the church's role in educating youth about morals by collaborating with schools.
 2. Offer a model for initiatives focused on empowering youth morally.Non-State Actors (e.g., NGOs, faith-based organizations):
 1. Develop targeted programs that tackle the moral decline among youth.
 2. Advocate for investment in religious education and youth empowerment.Other Researchers:
 1. Provide a valuable reference for future academic research on moral education, character development, and youth behavior.
 2. Add to the expanding literature on the intersection of religion and character formation in education.

Methodology

This study adopts a survey research design to examine the role of Christian religious studies in addressing moral decadence among secondary school students in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State. Data was collected using structured questionnaires administered to 100 respondents. The responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages.

The population consists of students from selected secondary schools, with respondents chosen through simple random sampling. The state, which has 20 Local Government Areas, is divided according to the 3 Senatorial Districts, namely, Ogun Central Senatorial District with 6 Local Government Areas, Ogun East Senatorial District with 9 Local Government Areas, and Ogun West Senatorial District with 5 Local Government Areas. Six secondary schools were

selected, with two from each Senatorial District. The names of the selected schools are:

Abeokuta Grammar School, Abeokuta, and Abiola International School, Abeokuta, are located in Ogun Central Senatorial District. Ijebu Igbo Grammar School, Ijebu Igbo, and Molipa High School, Ijebu-Ode, are situated in Ogun East Senatorial District. Comprehensive High School, Ayetoro, and Yewa College, Ilaro, are located in Ogun West Senatorial District. A total of 50 students from each of the six selected secondary schools constituted the sample for the study, which employed a purposive sampling technique. Also, a total of 300 copies of the questionnaire were administered to both male and female students, especially from the senior secondary schools of the target population.

Results and Analysis

Research Question 1: What is students' understanding of the concept and significance of Christian Religious Studies (CRS) in addressing moral decadence?

Table 3: Students' understanding of the concept and significance of Christian Religious Studies (CRS) in addressing moral decadence.

S/N	Items	Agree F(%)	Disagree F(%)
1	Christian Religious Studies is a subject that teaches core Christian values, including love, honesty, integrity, and respect.	80(80%)	20(20%)
2	Christian Religious Studies provides a framework for ethical decision-making.	70(70%)	30(30%)
3	plays a crucial role not just in individual moral development but also in positively impacting the community.	86(86%)	14(14%)
4	Christian Religious Studies is a means of encouraging reflection and self-examination.	82(82%)	18(18%)
5	Christian Religious Studies is significant for the holistic development of youths.	84(84%)	16(16%)

Source: Field work, 2025.

These responses reflect varying perspectives that students might have regarding the importance and influence of Christian Religious Studies on their moral development and behavior. In particular, Table 3 under Research Question 1 above shows that 80 of the respondents (80%) agreed that Christian Religious

Studies is a subject that teaches core Christian values, such as love, honesty, integrity, and respect. They believe these values are essential for guiding moral behavior and countering the negative influences that lead to moral decadence in society. At the same time, 20 of the respondents (20%) disagreed with the statement. Seventy (70) of the respondents representing (70%) agreed that Christian Religious studies provide a framework for ethical decision-making. They believe that the teachings from the Bible and other religious texts help them to evaluate their choices in light of moral principles, making them more aware of the implications of their actions. However, 30 of the respondents (30%) disagreed with the statement. Furthermore, 86 of the respondents representing (86%) agreed that Christian Religious studies play a crucial role not just in individual moral development but also in positively impacting the community. These respondents believe that by practicing the lessons learned in CRS, they can contribute to a more ethical and responsible society, thereby reducing instances of crime and immorality. In contrast, 14 respondents (14%) disagreed with the statement.

Eighty-two of the respondents (82%) agreed that Christian Religious Studies is a means of encouraging reflection and self-examination. In this way, they believe that through discussions of moral dilemmas and real-life applications of faith-based teachings, they develop a stronger sense of self-awareness and responsibility regarding their actions and their effects on others; however, 18 of the respondents (18%) disagreed with the statement. Eighty-four of the respondents (84%) agreed that Christian Religious studies are significant for the youths' holistic development. They recognize that the subject does not merely focus on religious teachings but also addresses social responsibility and community values, helping them to understand their roles as active, morally responsible citizens within a diverse society. However, 16 of the respondents (16%) disagreed with the statement. Furthermore, this study agreed that there are students' understanding of the concept and essence of Christian religious curbing moral decadence.

Research Question 2: What are the various forms of moral decadence that youths are engaged in?

Table 4: Various forms of moral decadence that youths are engaged in.

S/N	Items	Agree	Disagree
		F(%)	F(%)
6	Many youths are involved in substance abuse, including alcohol, marijuana, and other drugs.	88(88%)	12 (12%)
7	Youths frequently engage in cyberbullying and other forms of online misconduct.	82(82%)	18(18%)

8	Premarital sexual activities among youths are a key aspect of moral decadence observed today.	80(80%)	20(20%)
9	There is a prevalent culture of disrespect for authority figures, including teachers and parents.	86(86%)	14(14%)
10	There is an alarming rise in materialism and consumerism among youths.	87(87%)	13(13%)

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table 4 of research question 2 above shows that 88 of the respondents representing (88%) agreed that many youths are involved in substance abuse, including alcohol, marijuana, and other drugs. This indicates that the majority of the youths have experimented with drugs or alcohol by the time they reach secondary school, highlighting a significant concern for their health and moral well-being. Only 12 of the respondents (12%) disagreed with the statement. Eighty-two of the respondents, which represents (82%), agreed that cyber crime is a natural immoral decadence the youths are involved in, and the extent to which they are involved in it, while 18 of the respondents, representing (18%), disagreed with the statement. This study reveals that around 20-25% of adolescents have experienced or participated in cyberbullying, which reflects a troubling trend in their interactions and social dynamics in digital spaces. Eighty of the respondents, which represents (80%), agreed that rape is also a natural immoral decadence the youths are involved in, and to what extent they are involved in it, while 20 of the respondents, representing (20%), disagreed with the statement. Research shows that nearly 40% of secondary school students in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State have reported being sexually active, indicating a growing normalization of such behaviors despite cultural and religious teachings against them. Eighty-six of the respondents (86%) agreed that kidnapping and thuggery are natural immoral decadence the youths are involved in, and the extent to which they are involved in it, while 14 of the respondents (14%) disagreed with the statement. In Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, it has been noted that about 35% of students admit to frequently questioning or disrespecting school rules and authority, which can exacerbate issues related to discipline and moral values.

Eighty-seven of the respondents (87%) agreed that cultism is a naturally immoral decadence the youths are involved in, and the extent to which they are involved in it, while 13 of the respondents (13%) disagreed with the statement. Hence, this finding suggests that there are various forms of immoral decadence that youths are involved in, and the extent to which they are involved in them. Many students prioritize wealth and possessions over moral and ethical values. In Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, surveys indicate that over 50% of youths believe

personal success is defined by material wealth, showcasing a departure from traditional moral values. These responses provide insight into the various forms of moral decadence that youths are involved in and offer an understanding of the extent to which these behaviors are present in their lives.

Research Question 3: What are some of the key factors contributing to the promotion of moral decadence among students in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State?

Table 5: Some key factors contributing to the promotion of moral decadence among students in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State

S/N	Items	Agree F(%)	Disagree F(%)
11	Peer pressure is a significant factor influencing moral decadence among students in the Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State	90(90%)	10 (10%)
12	The portrayal of violence, substance use, and sexual promiscuity plays a crucial role in shaping adolescent perceptions of acceptable behavior.	80(80%)	20(20%)
13	A lack of strong parental guidance and involvement can lead to increased moral decay.	86(86%)	14(14%)
14	Living in challenging socioeconomic conditions can also drive youths toward moral decadence.	70(70%)	30(30%)
15	The decline in religious and ethical education in schools and homes is contributing to moral decadence.	90 (90%)	10 (10%)

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table 3, which addresses research question 3, highlights important factors contributing to the moral decline of students in the Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State. An overwhelming 90% of respondents feel that peer pressure is a significant factor, as young people often engage in risky behaviors to fit in with their peers. Moreover, 80% believe that the media's portrayal of violence, drug use, and promiscuity shapes adolescents' views on what is considered acceptable behavior, which may normalize immoral actions. The research also indicates that 86% of participants think a lack of parental guidance plays a role in moral decay, with many parents being either too lenient or disengaged to instill the correct values. Socioeconomic challenges are another issue, with 70% stating that poverty and limited opportunities can lead to unethical behavior as individuals strive for survival or social status. Additionally, 90% believe that the decline of religious and ethical education, both at home and in schools, significantly contributes to the

erosion of moral values. Without a solid foundation, students often struggle to establish a clear moral compass. These findings collectively underscore a complex interplay of social, familial, and environmental factors that influence youth behavior. The study calls for urgent community, educational, and parental initiatives to address these negative trends and foster ethical development among young people.

Research Question 4: What measures can be implemented to curb the increasing rate of moral decadence among students in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State?

Table 6: Some measures that can be implemented to curb the increasing rate of moral decadence among students in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State.

S/N	Items	Agree	Disagree
		F(%)	F(%)
16	Moral education should be made a compulsory subject from primary to tertiary levels to instill moral values, character, and civic responsibilities in students.	64(64%)	36(36%)
17	To combat moral decadence in Nigeria, the government must decriminalize political leadership.	80(80%)	20(20%)
18	Leaders and CRS teachers must learn the importance of setting a good example in an attempt to mold character.	76(76%)	24(24%)
19	Implementing comprehensive education programs that focus on moral and ethical values can be effective.	70(70%)	30(30%)
20	Improving access to counseling and support services for youths can play a significant role in addressing moral issues.	89(89%)	11(11%)

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table 6 of research question 4 above shows that 64 of the respondents representing (64%) agreed that moral education should be made a compulsory subject from primary to tertiary levels to instill moral values, character, and civic responsibilities in students. In comparison, 36 of the respondents representing (36%) disagreed to the statement. Eighty of the respondents, which represents (80%), agreed that in order to combat moral decadence in Nigeria, the government must decriminalize political leadership. Only 20 of the respondents (20%) disagreed with the statement. Ninety-six of the respondents (96%) agreed that leaders and Christian Religious Studies teachers must learn the importance of

showing a good example in an attempt to mould character, while only 4 of the respondents, who represent 4% disagreed with the statement.

Seventy of the respondents representing (70%) agreed that implementing comprehensive education programs that focus on moral and ethical values can be effective, while 30 of the respondents representing (30%) disagreed to the statement. Eighty-nine of the respondents representing (89%) agreed that improving access to counseling and support services for youths can play a significant role in addressing moral issues. Providing resources such as guidance counselors, mental health professionals, and programs focused on conflict resolution and coping strategies can help students navigate challenges that may lead to moral behaviors. Only 11 of the respondents representing (11%) disagreed to the statement.

These responses outline specific, actionable measures that can be taken to address and reduce the increasing rate of moral decadence among students in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State and Nigeria in general.

Concept of Christian Religious Studies (CRS)

Christian Religious Studies is an academic discipline that focuses on the teachings, history, and ethical principles of Christianity. It aims to promote moral uprightness, instill godly character, and encourage peaceful coexistence. CRS was introduced in Nigerian schools to instill discipline and ethical values (Oluoch-Suleh, E. and Ekene, 2020). The subject teaches students the importance of honesty, humility, and respect for others, thereby providing a strong moral foundation.

There is political instability at all levels of governance, and the love of money has taken over all aspects of life in Nigeria. The spiritual drive of the youth is weak, while the moral life of students in schools is similarly decaying.

The purpose of Christian education is to direct the process of human development toward God's objective for man: godliness of character and action as stated in 2 Timothy 3:17, "that the man of God may be perfect, thoroughly furnished unto all good works."

In order to achieve this objective, the major curriculum contents of the early missionary educational system included Bible Knowledge, Arithmetic, and English for communication (ProjectList Nigeria, 2025). To fully implement the curriculum, adequate attention was given to the understanding of the place of God in human life (Oluoch-Suleh and Osuji, 2020). Bible Knowledge became a core subject taught at all school levels. According to Onovughe (2008), during the missionary era, Bible Knowledge—now Christian Religious Studies—was the central subject. However, after Nigeria's independence, the government took over schools and reviewed the curriculum in 1983 due to criticisms that colonial

education was too arts-oriented and lacked relevance to Nigeria's political and infrastructural development (Njoku and Njoku, 2015).

Christian religious education remains crucial for promoting moral values in Nigeria. According to Ajibola, (2023), the controversial curriculum has been reverted to its original form, allowing both Islamic and Christian Religious Studies to be taught as legitimate subjects that foster nationalistic values. This paper, however, argues that religious curricula should be actively restructured to be more practical and relevant. The inclusion of Christian Religious Education in the curriculum can help mitigate Nigeria's social ills. Effective religious pedagogical approaches have emerged as contextual responses to students' diverse learning capabilities, ensuring that religious literacy is accessible and relevant (Lytra, Gregory, and Ilankuberan, 2016).

According to Victor-Akinyemi and Ayedogbon, (2024), the major aims of inclusion of CRS in Nigerian school curriculum are as follows:

- i. To raise a generation of people who can think for themselves.
- ii. To raise people that can respect the views and findings of others.
- iii. To raise people that respect dignity of labour.
- iv. To raise people that can respect moral values stated in the national aims as good citizens.
- v. To prepare learners for useful living through inculcation of Christian attitudes and values.
- vi. To prepare learners for their salvation in heaven with God Almighty.
- vii. To prepare learners for useful life of peaceful coexistence in the society.
- viii. To prepare learners to be able to adapt to a new of Jesus Christ to be able to love one another as Christ did.
- ix. To prepare learners to practice Christian discipline and moulding of moral characters.
- x. To shape the human behaviour and moral values

Purpose of Christian Religious Studies

The integration of Christian Religious Studies (CRS) into the educational system plays a pivotal role in shaping the moral and spiritual lives of students. Abolarin and Babalola (2020) argue that Christian education is instrumental in shaping the moral compass of students, urging them to embody virtues such as integrity and respect for societal norms. Through the study of the Bible and Christian teachings, students engage with concepts of justice, love, and service, which are central to responsible citizenship.

Concept of Moral Decadence

Moral decadence signifies the decline of ethical values and standards within a society. Morality has been described as the ability to discern right from wrong and act accordingly, suggesting that a breakdown in moral values leads to various forms of societal dysfunction (Victor-Akinyemi and Ayedogbon). In educational settings, this decline can manifest as increased instances of dishonesty, substance abuse, and disrespect for authority. Notably, these behaviors are often influenced by external factors, such as peer pressure and media representation.

Several factors have been identified as contributing to this moral decline among secondary school students, including inadequate parenting and pervasive negative media influences (Bolu-Steve et al., 2022). The contemporary media landscape often glorifies immoral behavior, thereby shaping the perceptions and behaviors of impressionable youth. Consequently, students may struggle to uphold the ethical standards promoted by their religious education. Furthermore, the phenomenon of moral decadence often creates a cyclical effect, where declining values contribute to societal issues such as increased crime rates and decreased civic responsibility. This underscores the importance of CRS in counteracting these trends. By instilling biblical virtues and promoting a sense of accountability among students, CRS aims to mitigate the impact of moral decline. Conclusion In conclusion, the study of Christian Religious Studies serves a dual purpose: it shapes the moral and spiritual lives of students while countering the pervasive issue of moral decadence in society. By instilling enduring values and encouraging critical engagement with moral dilemmas, CRS plays a vital role in character development. Understanding the manifestations and causes of moral decay is crucial for educators, policymakers, and religious leaders who seek to cultivate a morally upright and responsible citizenry. With the growing challenges posed by contemporary society, the role of Christian education in cultivating ethical frameworks for students cannot be overstated.

Manifestation of Moral Decadence

Manifestations of Moral Decadence in Nigeria. Moral decadence has become a pressing concern in Nigeria, manifesting in various troubling forms that reflect the deterioration of ethical standards across society. The following are some key manifestations of moral decadence observed in Nigerian society.

1. Sexual Immorality

One of the most alarming manifestations of moral decadence is sexual immorality, which includes early pregnancies, sexual harassment, and even prostitution among youths. The increasing prevalence of teenage pregnancies highlights the failure of both educational and family systems to impart responsible sexual behavior. According to Bolu-Steve *et al* (2023), many young girls,

pressured by societal norms and peer behavior, find themselves vulnerable in situations that lead to unplanned pregnancies. Furthermore, sexual harassment has become a pervasive issue in educational institutions, where students often face exploitation from peers and authority figures alike. The normalization of such behaviors is profoundly troubling, indicating a significant breakdown in moral values (Courtois and Gendron 2017).

2. *Cybercrime.*

Cybercrime, particularly internet fraud popularly known as "Yahoo-Yahoo," represents another facet of moral decadence. Many young individuals view cybercrime as a lucrative alternative to conventional employment, motivated by the allure of quick wealth and social status (Omokhabi 2024). This trend has led many youths to embrace fraudulent activities, which ultimately erodes trust within society. The rise of cybercrime is indicative of a society grappling with economic challenges, where the desire for instant gratification increasingly overshadows the values of hard work and integrity.

3. *Cultism*

Cultism has emerged as a significant contributor to moral decadence, leading to gang-related violence and clashes within schools. These secret societies often foster a culture of fear and intimidation, compelling students to engage in illicit activities. Ajayi (2022) notes that the presence of cult groups in educational institutions has escalated to a point where academic pursuits are frequently interrupted by violent confrontations. The involvement in cultic activities fosters an environment of insecurity, compounding the moral decay experienced in Nigerian society, particularly among the youth.

4. *Drug Abuse*

The excessive consumption of illicit substances underscores a critical aspect of moral decadence affecting Nigerian youth. Drug abuse has permeated various demographics, often becoming a coping mechanism for emotional and psychological distress. Obadeji et al. (2020) point out that the normalization of substance use among adolescents signals a significant lapse in moral guidance. It has detrimental effects not only on personal health but also on academic performance and social relationships, further compounding society's moral decline.

5. *Examination Malpractice*

Examination malpractice is another glaring manifestation of moral decadence, undermining the integrity of educational systems. Students often engage in dishonest practices, such as cheating, to secure favorable outcomes (Cleto 2024). As observed by Pinga *et al.* (2024), this behavior reflects a broader societal issue

where the value of hard work and honest effort is increasingly negated by the pursuit of success at any cost. Such trends raise concerns about the quality of education and the future capabilities of graduates entering the workforce.

Causes of Moral Decadence

Causes of Moral Decadence in Nigeria. The alarming rise in moral decadence among youths in Nigeria can be attributed to a multitude of interrelated social, economic, and technological factors. Addressing these causes is essential in understanding the broader context of moral decline and formulating effective interventions. The following sections outline some of the primary causes contributing to moral decadence among Nigerian youths.

1. Parental Negligence

One of the most significant contributors to moral decadence is parental negligence. Many parents are preoccupied with their careers and daily survival, leaving little time to provide adequate moral guidance and supervision for their children. It has been said that this lack of parental involvement can lead to children developing misguided values and behaviors as they seek validation and support from external sources (Mao *et al.*, 2020). As children navigate their formative years without proper guidance, they are more susceptible to negative influences, often resulting in poor decision-making that contributes to moral decline.

2. Economic Hardship

Economic hardship serves as another significant factor contributing to moral decay among young people. High unemployment rates and financial struggles compel many young people to seek alternative sources of income, sometimes choosing paths that involve criminal activities. The desperation to achieve financial stability often leads youths to engage in cybercrime, theft, and other illegal practices, as they perceive these actions as viable means of survival (Modupe and Adelus 2020). The resulting moral decay is exacerbated by socio-economic instability, wherein the lack of legitimate opportunities instills a sense of hopelessness among youths.

3. *Negative Media*

The ever-increasing exposure to negative media influences plays a critical role in shaping the moral landscape for Nigerian youths. The proliferation of television shows, movies, and social media content that glamorize unethical behavior fosters a culture that normalizes immorality. It has been observed that the saturation of immoral content in contemporary media cultivates a desensitization effect, where young viewers become numb to ethical violations and thus less likely to uphold moral values (Modupe and Adelusi 2022). This constant bombardment of negative influences can lead to the erosion of personal ethics and a shift toward accepting immoral behavior as the norm.

4. *Peer Pressure*

Peer pressure remains a significant factor influencing moral behavior among young people. During adolescence, individuals are particularly susceptible to the opinions and behaviors of their peers, often prioritizing social acceptance over moral considerations. It was also noted that the desire to fit in with friends and social groups can lead to compromised values, as youths engage in actions they might otherwise avoid, such as substance abuse or criminal acts (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2025). This social dynamic creates a challenging environment for young people striving to adhere to high moral standards.

5. *Weak Religious Values*

The declining emphasis on religious and moral education contributes significantly to the overall moral decay observed in Nigerian society (Alaka-Osinowo 2024). Many religious institutions, which should serve as safeguards against moral decline, have shifted their focus toward commercial pursuits rather than fostering spiritual growth among young people (Onuorah, 2022). This shift leads to a weakened moral foundation, where young people lack the guidance necessary to navigate ethical dilemmas. Without a robust framework grounded in ethical teaching from religious institutions, youths may struggle to establish their moral compasses, leading to increased instances of immorality.

Roles of Christian Religious Studies in Addressing Moral Decadence

The Role of Christian Religious Studies in Addressing Moral Decadence Among Secondary School Students in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State. Christian Religious Studies (CRS) plays a crucial role in combating moral decadence among secondary school students in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State. By promoting ethical values and spiritual development, CRS can significantly influence the moral fabric of the community. The following sections outline the various roles that CRS can play in addressing this critical issue, supported by relevant academic literature.

1. *Moral Education*

The foundation of tackling moral decay lies in effective moral education. CRS offers students a framework for understanding ethical principles and social responsibilities. As Omomia and Omomia (2024) note, religious education gives students the ability to distinguish right from wrong, instilling virtues such as honesty, respect, and responsibility. Through structured lessons that include biblical teachings, students learn why ethical behavior matters in daily life. Regular discussions on moral dilemmas and case studies can help them put these principles into practice, fostering a generation that values integrity and accountability (Inameti and Udoh 2023).

2. *Spiritual Guidance*

In addition to moral education, CRS provides essential spiritual guidance that encourages students to embrace a faith-based discipline. This method helps foster a sense of integrity and responsibility in their actions. It has been argued that spiritual guidance builds personal relationships with God through prayer, worship, and reflection, reminding students of their duties to themselves and their communities (Galenka et al, 2024). Students who participate in spiritual practices are often more resilient to negative influences, which decreases misconduct and promotes their overall character development.

3. *Youth Empowerment Programs*

CRS can greatly promote youth empowerment by hosting seminars and workshops focused on moral values and ethical living. These programs can cover important topics such as the effects of immoral behavior, the importance of character development, and ways to handle societal pressures. According to John (2025), such initiatives offer practical skills and knowledge needed to navigate the complexities of modern society while maintaining strong moral principles. By engaging local leaders, clergy, and educators as facilitators, these empowerment programs can strengthen community support for moral growth among young people.

4. *Parental Involvement*

The role of parents in their children's moral development cannot be overstated. CRS can actively engage parents by educating them on their responsibilities in fostering moral values at home.

Workshops, informational sessions, and collaborative activities can help parents understand the importance of maintaining open communication about ethical behavior and providing consistent guidance. By equipping parents with tools and resources, CRS fosters strong home environments where moral issues can be openly discussed and addressed. This partnership between parents and the school

reinforces the values imparted through CRS and promotes a holistic approach to character development.

5. School Curriculum Integration

Finally, integrating CRS into the school curriculum as a core subject ensures that all students receive a consistent moral education throughout their secondary education. Yaro (2020) emphasizes that making CRS a central component of the academic experience guarantees that moral teachings are reinforced across various subjects and contexts. Additionally, incorporating community service projects within the CRS curriculum provides students with hands-on experience in practicing their values, fostering a sense of responsibility and community engagement. Such exposure solidifies the practical application of ethical principles in everyday life.

Finally, the roles of Christian Religious Studies in addressing moral decadence among secondary school students in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State, are multifaceted and deeply interlinked. Through moral education, spiritual guidance, youth empowerment programs, parental involvement, and curriculum integration, CRS can play a transformative role in cultivating a generation committed to ethical living and community service. By reinforcing these principles and promoting active participation from both students and their families, CRS holds the potential to foster a more morally conscious and responsible society.

Summary

The alarming rate of moral decadence in Nigeria is a pressing issue that has been exacerbated by the failures of various social institutions, including the family, schools, and religious organizations (Napbut *et al.*, 2024). While these entities promote ethical behavior and the fear of the Lord, many have fallen short in openly condemning immoral practices. Schools, once seen as bastions of moral education, have come under scrutiny for providing environments that appear permissive toward indecency and unethical behavior. This calls for a collective effort to address the root causes of moral decline and to restore ethical standards across all facets of Nigerian society.

Conclusion

The study establishes that CRS plays a crucial role in curbing moral decadence among secondary school students. It highlights that moral education, religious teachings, and parental guidance are essential in fostering ethical behavior. The findings reveal that various factors, including economic hardship and peer pressure, contribute to moral decline. CRS can serve as an effective tool in addressing these issues by instilling discipline and promoting moral consciousness among students.

Recommendations

1. Integrate moral education into the curriculum – CRS should be made compulsory at all educational levels.
2. Encourage parental involvement – Parents should actively participate in their children's moral education.
3. Strengthen religious teachings – Schools should collaborate with religious institutions to provide spiritual guidance.
4. Monitor media exposure – Parents and educators should regulate students' access to harmful media content.
5. Enhance government policies – Authorities should implement policies that promote ethical governance and youth empowerment.

By adopting these measures, moral decadence among secondary school students can be significantly reduced, leading to a more disciplined and responsible generation.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study shows that Christian Religious Studies (CRS) plays a critical role in addressing moral decadence among secondary school students in Odeda Local Government Area and Nigeria at large. It points out important values taught in CRS—such as honesty, respect, empathy, and forgiveness—that can help improve moral values in society. The research also discusses the roles of various stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and religious organizations, in fostering moral education. Additionally, it addresses challenges like limited resources and student disengagement, and suggests reforms in policy and curriculum to make CRS more effective in tackling moral issues in Nigerian secondary schools.

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